

Data Use Agreement (DUA)

IRPose16: A Dataset for Human Pose Estimation Using Infrared Imaging and Low-Cost Reflective Markers

1. Parties

This Data Use Agreement ("Agreement") is entered into by the Centre for Human Movement Analytics, Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT), Chennai, India ("Data Provider"), and any individual or organization accessing the IRPose16 dataset ("Data Recipient").

2. Description of the Data

The IRPose16 dataset contains infrared (IR) and RGB video recordings, 2D human pose keypoint annotations (16 anatomical keypoints per frame), calibration data, and associated metadata collected from human participants performing predefined motion sequences.

3. Ethical Compliance and Consent

All participants provided written informed consent for participation and research data sharing. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Vellore Institute of Technology, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

4. Permitted Use

The dataset may be used for lawful research, benchmarking, algorithm development, educational activities, and other purposes consistent with the terms of this Agreement.

5. Prohibited Use

Users shall not attempt to identify or re-identify participants, use the data for surveillance or biometric identification, redistribute the raw dataset, or use the data in ways that violate ethical or legal standards.

6. Data Security

Recipients must store the data securely and prevent unauthorized access or redistribution.

7. Publications and Attribution

Any publications or derivative works using IRPose16 must cite the associated Scientific Data article.

8. Disclaimer

The dataset is provided "as is" without warranties. The Data Provider is not liable for misuse.

9. Termination

Violation of this agreement results in termination of access and required deletion of all copies.

10. Governing Law

This Agreement shall be governed by the laws of India.

Acceptance of this Agreement is implied by requesting access to, downloading, or using the dataset. By requesting access through the repository, users acknowledge that they have read and agree to the terms of this agreement.